

CONTEXTUALIZED SEGMENTAL WORKSHEETS FOR LEARNERS (SWL): A CONCEPTUAL APPROACH IN LEARNING INTEGERS AMONG GRADE 11 LEARNERS

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ABSTRACT

Mastering integer operations is essential for building a strong mathematical foundation, as it enables students to confidently engage with more complex mathematical concepts and problem-solving tasks. High number of students struggle with numeracy, is among the struggles of Mathematics teachers in Malitbog National High School. Contextualized Segmental Worksheets for Learners (SWL) is a researcher-made supplementary material which aimed to enhance the understanding of integer operations among Grade 11 learners through contextualized, segmented and structured activities. The study employed a one-group pretest-post-test experimental design, involving 25 Grade 11 learners identified as "not proficient" in numeracy. A pre-test was administered to assess their initial performance, followed by a five-week intervention utilizing the contextualized SWL. A post-test was then conducted to measure improvements in their proficiency. Results revealed that, during the pre-test, respondents exhibited a "not proficient" level of performance. After the intervention, their post-test scores improved to a "nearly proficient" level, indicating a progress in understanding integer operations. Moreover, statistical analysis confirmed a significant difference between the pre-test and post-test scores, demonstrating the effectiveness of the intervention in enhancing learners' numeracy skills. This study highlights the importance of contextualized and experiential learning in addressing numeracy challenges. It recommends that teachers integrate contextualized Segmental Worksheets for Learners into their instructional strategies to improve learners' performance. Additionally, further research is encouraged to refine and expand the implementation of such interventions for broader impact.

INTRODUCTION

Numeracy involves the knowledge, skills, behaviors, and attitudes needed to apply mathematics effectively in everyday situations (Tabor et al., 2020). It is essential for success in both academic and professional settings (White, 2024). However, global assessments like PISA and TIMSS reveal a decline in math performance, with the Philippines ranking lowest among 58 countries in Grade 4 math and science (World Economic Forum, 2023; Baclig, 2020). The COVID-19 pandemic has further intensified these learning gaps. Aligned with the United Nations' SDG 4, which promotes quality and inclusive education, the Department of Education (DepEd) developed the Basic Education Research Agenda (BERA) to guide research and improve teaching and learning (Regional Memorandum No. 329, s. 2023). At Malitbog National High School, 15% of Grade 11 learners got "not proficient" level in the Enhanced-Regional Unified Numeracy Test (E-RUNT), primarily due to difficulties with basic integer operations. This study focuses on these 25 non-proficient learners, aiming to improve their skills using Contextualized Segmental Worksheets for Learners (SWL)—a tool developed to strengthen their understanding of fundamental operations. The goal is to support both students and teachers in enhancing numeracy and overall classroom learning.

Mathematics plays a crucial role in intellectual development by improving problem-solving skills, logical reasoning, and mental agility. It also builds important traits such as patience, willpower, and creativity (Sam, 2024). Although many see mathematics as complex, it is closely tied to daily life and technological progress—from simple calculations to advancements in artificial intelligence and data analysis (Ribeiro, 2024).

Yet, even as more people recognize the value of mathematics, major challenges remain in how it is taught and learned. A common issue is that students struggle due to misunderstandings and too much focus on memorizing steps. Skemp (1976, as cited in Herheim, 2023) called this "instrumental understanding"—learning procedures without grasping the concepts behind them. In contrast, educational thinkers like Bruner (1966, in Hurrell, 2021) and Kilpatrick et al. (2001, in Maoto et al., 2018) highlight the importance of conceptual learning rooted in real-life situations. Vygotsky (1978, in Topçiu & Myftiu, 2015) adds to this by promoting guided instruction within the learner's zone of proximal development.

Beyond cognitive barriers, emotional and psychological factors also impact math learning. Mathematics anxiety (Tobias, 1993; Bicer, et al., 2020) and fixed beliefs about ability (Dweck, 2006 in Dweck, et al., 2019) lower students' confidence and motivation. These issues are often worsened when students cannot connect what they learn to real-life situations, highlighting the need for more meaningful and relevant instruction (Boaler, 1998 in Schoenfeld, 2016).

More specific challenges appear in certain topics, such as integers. Many students struggle with understanding positive and negative numbers, recognizing signs, and performing mixed operations (Lobo, 2024; Harris, 2023; Ojose, 2015). These problems usually stem from weak foundational knowledge and conceptual confusion, which makes it harder for students to apply procedures correctly.

To address these challenges, concrete and hands-on learning is essential. Research shows that using real objects and experiences helps students understand and stay engaged. McLeod (2023) links this method to experiential learning theory. Similarly, Southeast Asia Primary Learning Metrics (2019) reports that Filipino students often fall behind in math partly due to limited use of practical tools. Materials like physical models and manipulatives have been shown to boost problem-solving skills and understanding (Savas & Beverly, 2024; Liljedahl, 2020; Warren, 2024). Using real-life examples also helps students remember better and enjoy learning more (Lindsay, n.d.).

For struggling and non-numerate learners, this type of contextualized teaching is especially important. DepEd Order No. 39, s. 2016 supports this approach, emphasizing that lessons tied to real-world tasks make learning more effective. When students can relate concepts to daily life, they find them more meaningful and easier to understand (Brown et al., 1989; Boaler, 1998; Freudenthal, 1991).

A conceptual approach, rather than rote memorization, leads to better learning. When students connect ideas meaningfully, they remember longer and can use their knowledge in new situations (Kilpatrick et al., 2001; Hiebert & Lefevre, 1986; Tessa School, 2024; Hodkowski, 2024). Focusing on concepts over procedures results in more lasting and useful learning outcomes.

To support this, segmental worksheets have proven to be helpful tools. By dividing lessons into smaller parts, they encourage independent and self-paced learning. These worksheets help build skills in problem-solving and math understanding (Peak, 2021; Juliana et al., 2022). Studies show they improve focus, memory, and overall performance (Kwakye, 2022; Widodo et al., 2023; Bryant et al., 2020).

Worksheets become even more effective when designed to fit real-world contexts. When based on frameworks like Multiple Intelligences Theory and Realistic Mathematics Education (RME), they cater to different learning styles and help build numeracy skills (Inan, 2017; Hasibuan et al., 2018). Multimedia-enhanced worksheets also make learning more engaging and help improve understanding and motivation (Peralta, 2023; Zarate et al., 2022; Mairing, 2021; Emballa, 2022).

In learning integers specifically, students often face difficulties due to the abstract nature of the topic and persistent misconceptions (Hanifa et al., 2024; Kurniasi et al., 2024). Using real-world examples and RME-based worksheets can help students overcome these challenges (Root et al., 2018; Maharani et al., 2023; Saputro et al., 2020).

Lastly, digital worksheets offer additional benefits. They provide flexibility and allow students to learn in ways that suit them best (Sari et al., 2024; Amir & Septiarini, 2023). Broader research shows that segmental and contextualized worksheets support early math development, logical thinking, and meaningful learning across diverse student groups (Cheung et al., 2018; Reyes et al., 2024; Sukasno et al., 2024).

Research Questions

This study aims to determine the effect of Contextualized Segmental Worksheets for Learners (SWL) on the performance of Grade 11 learners of Malitbog National High School, during the School Year 2024-2025.

Specifically, this study aims to answer the following questions:

1. What is the Pre-test performance of the respondents?
 2. What is the Post-test performance of the respondents?
 3. Is there a significant difference in the pre-test and post-test performance of the respondents?
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METHODOLOGY

This one-group pre-test post-test study aimed to determine the effect of contextualized Segmental Worksheets for Learners (SWL) on the numeracy performance of the respondents. One-group pretest-post-test experimental design was used to measure variables before and after an intervention to determine its impact. This helped establish trends and changes due to the intervention. According to Maxwell (2016), there were two primary phases of measurement in the pretest-post-test design. Before the intervention was implemented, a pre-test was given to determine the respondents' current status on the outcome variable. A post-test was given following the intervention to gauge whether the outcome variable had changed. By comparing the pretest and post-test results, this approach aided in assessing the intervention's efficacy.

Participants

The respondents of the study were the twenty-five (25) Grade 11 learners Malitbog National High School, Schools District of Calinog II, Schools Division of Iloilo for the School Year 2024-2025.

Moreover, the instrument to gather the pretest data was the Mid E-RUNT while Post E-RUNT was used for post-test. The instrument is a standardized test comprising forty word problems focused on integer operations, 10 items for each operation (addition, subtraction, multiplication and division).

For the intervention, a researcher-made Contextualized SWL was used. This served as supplementary learning materials designed to enhance students' understanding of integer operations through structured segmental activities. The SWL

underwent validation by two mathematics teachers for content and face validity, as well as by one English teacher for grammatical accuracy. The material was assessed using the Evaluation Rating Sheet for Print Resources from the Guidelines and Processes for Learning Resources Management and Development System (LRMDS) Assessment & Evaluation of the Department of Education.

Data Gathering Procedure

The researcher, with the assistance of the research adviser, identified a problem to be undertaken. The manuscript was then prepared for concept defense. Relevant data were gathered, and the manuscript, along with validated instructional materials, was prepared for the pre-oral defense. After the pre-oral defense, permissions to conduct the study were sought from the office of the school head of Malitbog National High School, Malitbog Centro, Calinog, Iloilo.

The researcher conducted pre- test using Mid ERUNT before a five-week intervention for the identified respondents after confirming their willingness and cooperation to participate in the study. The objectives and purpose of the study were clearly explained to the respondents, who, beforehand, were assured of the strict confidentiality of their responses. After the five-week intervention, a post-test was conducted using Post ERUNT. The data were gathered based on the specific objectives of the study and were computed, tabulated, and presented in accordance with the research method adopted for analysis and interpretation

Data Analysis Procedure

The statistical tools used in analyzing the data were the mean, standard deviation and the t-test for dependent samples, with the level of significance set at 0.05. All statistical computations were performed using the Statistical Package for the Social Sciences (SPSS).

RESULTS

Descriptive Data Analysis

The Pre-Test Performance of The Respondents

The respondent's performance in the pre-test is shown in Table 1. During the pre-test, the respondents have "not proficient" performance ($M=8.84$, $SD=2.96$). It means that the respondents have a limited knowledge of the operations on integers considering their very low scores in the Mid E-RUNT.

Table 1
The Pre-test Performances of the respondents

Category	SD	Mean	%	Description
Pre-Test	2.96	8.84	22%	Not Proficient

Scale:

Mean	Description
90% – 100%	Highly Proficient
75% – 89%	Proficient
50% – 74%	Nearly Proficient
25% – 49%	Low Proficiency
0% – 24%	Not Proficient

The Post-Test Performance of The Respondents

The respondent's performance in the post- test is shown in Table 3. During the post-test, the respondents have "nearly proficient" performance. (M=20.68, SD=5.35). it means that there is a notable improvement compared to their pre-test performance, indicating that the respondents progressed in their understanding of integer operations in the Post E-RUNT.

Table 2
The Post-test Performances of the respondents

Category	SD	Mean	%	Description
Post -Test	5.35	20.68	52%	Nearly Proficient

Scale:

Mean	Description
90% – 100%	Highly Proficient
75% – 89%	Proficient
50% – 74%	Nearly Proficient
25% – 49%	Low Proficiency
0% – 24%	Not Proficient

Inferential Data Analysis

The Difference Between the Respondents' Pre-Test and Post-Test Performances

The difference in the performances of the respondents during the pre-test and post-test is shown in Table 4. The results of the dependent t-test indicate a significant difference ($p = 0.000$) between the pre-test and post-test performances. Since the p-value is less than 0.05, the null hypothesis, which states that there is no significant difference between the pre-test and post-test performances of the respondents, is rejected. The contextualized SWL significantly affect the performance of learners.

Table 3.

The Dependent t-Test Result for the Differences in the Pre-test and Post-test Performances of the respondents

Paired Variables	Mean	df	Mean Difference	t	Sig.
Pre test	8.84	24	11.84	13.836***	.000
Post test	20.68				

p<0.001

Conclusions

In view of the foregoing findings, the following conclusions were formulated:

The respondents had not yet acquired mastery of integer operations during the pre-test, as indicated by their "not proficient" level of performance. However, the post-test results show a notable improvement compared to their pre-test scores, suggesting that the respondents made progress in understanding integer operations. Although they did not reach the proficiency level, the increase in mean scores reflects a positive learning effect, indicating that the intervention contributed to their improved performance. Nevertheless, the findings also imply that further reinforcement or additional instructional strategies may be necessary to help learners attain higher levels of proficiency.

Furthermore, the results revealed a significant difference between the respondents' pre-test and post-test performance. This suggests that the Contextualized Segmental Worksheet Learning (SWL) was effective in improving the respondents' performance in integer operations.

Recommendations

Based on the findings, several recommendations are proposed to support and improve mathematics education. First, learners should aim to master the basic operations of integers to strengthen their math skills and achieve better performance.

Parents also play a crucial role by actively supporting their children's learning through encouragement, guidance, and by creating a positive study environment at home.

Mathematics teachers are encouraged to incorporate Contextualized Segmental Worksheets for Learners (SWL) into their lessons and to use experiential and interactive teaching strategies to boost student engagement and understanding. It is also important that they foster a supportive classroom atmosphere that promotes learning and growth.

The Department of Education (DepEd) is encouraged to implement programs that enhance the teaching and learning of mathematics, particularly to help students struggling with integer operations develop stronger conceptual understanding and problem-solving abilities. Moreover, the results of this study should be shared through publication in academic or peer-reviewed journals to contribute to the advancement of mathematics education.

Finally, further research is recommended to identify more effective strategies and interventions that can help improve students' mastery of integer operations and overall mathematical competence.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

This study followed proper ethical practices. Participants were clearly informed about the research and gave their consent before joining. A letter was also sent to parents to get their permission. The researcher made sure to protect the participants' privacy and keep their information safe. Two primary ethical principles were upheld: confidentiality and anonymity. Confidentiality was maintained by ensuring that no personal information was shared beyond the research team, while anonymity—representing a more rigorous standard—ensured that participants' identities remained undisclosed throughout the entire research process.

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REFERENCES

- Amir, M., & Septiarini, A. (2023). Mathematical Literacy-Oriented Student Worksheets for the Sidoarjo Context. *Formatif: Jurnal Ilmiah Pendidikan MIPA*. 13(1).
<http://dx.doi.org/10.30998/formatif.v13i1.12107>
- Baclig, C. E. (2020). PH's Grade 4 learners lowest in math, science around the world — int'l study. *Inquirer.net*. <https://newsinfo.inquirer.net/1370289/phs-grade-4-learners-lowest-in-math-science-around-the-world-study>
- Bicer, Ali & Perihan, Celal & Lee, Yujin. (2020). A Meta-Analysis: The Effects of CBT as a Clinic- & School-Based Treatment on Students' Mathematics Anxiety. *International Electronic Journal of Mathematics Education*. 15. 10.29333/iejme/7598.
- Boaler, J. (1998). *Experiencing School Mathematics: Teaching Styles, Sex, and Setting*. Open University Press.
- Brown, J. S., Collins, A., & Duguid, P. (1989). *Situated Cognition and the Culture of*

- Learning. *Educational Researcher*, 18 (1), 32-41.
- Bruner, J. S. (1966). *Toward a theory of instruction*. Harvard University Press.
- Bryant D.P., Bryant B.R., Dougherty B., Roberts G., Pfannenstiel K.H., & Lee J. (2020). Mathematics performance on integers of learners with mathematics difficulties. *Journal of Mathematical Behavior*, 58, art. no. 100776
- Cheung, S., Yang, X., Dulay, K., & McBride, C. (2018). Family and individual variables associated with young Filipino children's numeracy interest and competence. *British Journal of Developmental Psychology*, 36, 334–353. <https://doi.org/10.1111/bjdp.12222>.
- DepEd Order No. 39, s. 2016 - The effectiveness of contextualization of learning in the new normal
- Dweck, C. S. (2006). *Mindset: The new psychology of success*. Random House.
- Dweck, C. S., & Yeager, D. S. (2019). Mindsets: A View From Two Eras. *Perspectives on Psychological Science*, 14(3), 481-496. <https://doi.org/10.1177/1745691618804166>
- Emballa, R. O. (2022). Worksheet: remedial materials in teaching mathematics 10. *International Journal of Research Publications*. <https://doi.org/10.47119/ijrp1001061820223752>
- Freudenthal, H. (1991). *Revisiting Mathematics Education: China Lectures*. Springer Dordrecht. <https://doi.org/10.1007/0-306-47202-3>
- Hanifa, U. N., Pabawanto, S., & Fatimah, S. (2024). Identification of the Difficulties of Middle School Learners in Understanding the Mixed Operations of Integer. *KnE Social Sciences*. International Conference on Mathematics and Science Education (ICMScE 2022): Learning Models and Teaching Approaches. <https://doi.org/10.18502/kss.v9i13.15956>
- Harris, P. (2023). Why is reasoning about integers so hard?. *Math is FigureOutable*. <https://www.mathisfigureoutable.com/blog/why-is-reasoning-about-integers-so-hard>
- Hasibuan, A. M., Saragih, S., & Amry, Z. (2018). Development of Learning Materials Based on Realistic Mathematics Education to Improve Problem Solving Ability and Student Learning Independence. *International Electronic Journal of Mathematics Education*. <https://doi.org/10.29333/IEJME/4000>
- Herheim, R. On the origin, characteristics, and usefulness of instrumental and relational understanding. *Educ Stud Math* 113, 389–404 (2023). <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10649-023-10225-0>
- Hiebert, J., & Lefevre, P. (1986). Conceptual and procedural knowledge: The case of mathematics (pp. 1–27). Lawrence Erlbaum Associates, Inc.
- Hodkowski, N. (2024). When Teaching Learners Math, Concepts Matter More Than Process. *EdSurge*. <https://www.edsurge.com/news/2024-06-05>
- Hurrell, D. P. (2021). Conceptual knowledge OR Procedural knowledge OR Conceptual knowledge and Procedural knowledge: Why the conjunction is important for teachers. *Australian Journal of Teacher Education*, 46(2). <http://dx.doi.org/10.14221/ajte.2021v46n2.4>
- İnan, C. & Erkuş, S. (2017). The Effect of Mathematical Worksheets Based on Multiple Intelligences Theory on the Academic Achievement of the Learners in the 4th Grade Primary School. *Universal Journal of Educational Research*. DOI:

- 10.13189/ujer.2017.050810
Juliana, Netty & Ampera, Dina & Fariyah, & Baharuddin, & Sinukaban, Veronika. (2024). Digital Student Worksheets to Improving Students' Learning Independence. *Journal of Education Technology*. 8. 31-41. 10.23887/jet.v8i1.75433.
- Kilpatrick, J. & Swafford, J. & Findell, B. (2001). *Adding it up: Helping children learn mathematics*. National Academy Press.
- Kurniasi, R., Nurjanah, N., & Cahya, E. (2024). Students' learning obstacle in operations of integer. *Educenter : Jurnal Ilmiah Pendidikan*. 3. 59-67. 10.55904/educenter.v3i1.1107.
- Kwakye O., & Aggrey, J. (2022). The Teaching and Learning of Integer Operations: The Case of Number Rule and Conventional Method. *Journal of Education and Practice*. 13. 1-15. 10.7176/JEP/13-27-01.
- Liljedahl, P. (2020). *Building Thinking Classrooms in Mathematics, Grades K-12*. Corwin: A Sage Company
- Lindsay (n.d.). Sweet'n'Saucer. <https://sweetsauerfirsties.com/2021/03/14/why-little-learners-need-concrete-learning-during-math/>
- Lobo, W. (2024). Operations of Integers and Why Learners Find Them Difficult. LinkedIn. <https://www.linkedin.com/pulse/operations-integers-why-learners-find-them-difficult-winston-lobo-pu6uf/>
- Maharani, S., Susanti, V., Andari, T., Krisdiana, I., Astuti, I. (2023). Computational Thinking (CT)-based Student Worksheet to Improve the Mathematical Literacy of Mathematics Prospective Teacher. *Al-Ishlah Jurnal Pendidikan*. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.35445/alishlah.v15i3.4412>
- Mairing, J. P. (2021). Proving Abstract Algebra Skills with Problem-Based Learning Integrated with Videos and Worksheets. *Bolema*, 35(70), 1000–1015. <https://doi.org/10.1590/1980-4415V35N70A20>
- Maoto, S., Masha, K., & Mokwana, L. (2018). Teachers' learning and assessing of mathematical processes with emphasis on representations, reasoning and proof. *Pythagoras*, 39(1), a373. <https://doi.org/10.4102/pythagoras.v39i1.373>
- Maxwell KL, Wright VH. Evaluating the Effectiveness of Two Teaching Strategies to Improve Nursing Learners' Knowledge, Skills, and Attitudes About Quality Improvement and Patient Safety. *Nurs Educ Perspect*. 2016 Sep/Oct;37(5):291-292. doi: 10.1097/01.NEP.0000000000000043. PMID: 27740566.
- Mcleod, S. (2023). Kolb's learning Styles and Experiential Learning Cycle. *Simply Psychology*
- Ojose, B.(2015). *Common Misconceptions in Mathematics. Strategies to Correct Them*. University Press of America, Inc.
- Peak, L. (2021) *The Effects of Segmenting Worksheets on Independent Seatwork with Elementary Learners Delivered in a Remote Manner using Parents as Interventionist*. University of Southern Mississippi
- Peralta, J. B. (2023). Effectiveness Of Contextualized Learning Resource Material in Kindergarten. *International Journal of Advanced Multidisciplinary Studies*. https://www.ijams-bbp.net/wp-content/uploads/2024/03/1-IJAMS-JUNE-2023-558-569.pdf?utm_source=chatgpt.com
- Regional Memo No. 329 s. 2023 – Adoption of Regional Education Research Agenda

- Reyes, L., Atienza, A., & Calayag, M. (2024). The use of project BIBO in improving the numeracy rate of elementary schools in Candelaria East District. *Industry and Academic Research Review*. <https://doi.org/10.53378/iarr.924.112>.
- Ribeiro, D. (2024). Role of Mathematics in the Modern World. LinkedIn. <https://www.linkedin.com/pulse/role-mathematics-modern-world-diogo-ribeiro-c4kcf/>
- Root, J., Cox, S., Hammons, N., Saunders, A., Gilley, D. (2018). Contextualizing Mathematics: Teaching Problem Solving to Secondary Students with Intellectual and Developmental Disabilities. *Intellect Dev Disabil* 1 December 2018; 56 (6): 442–457. doi: <https://doi.org/10.1352/1934-9556-56.6.442>
- Sam (2024). Why Maths Matters: Real World Applications of Maths. Superprof Blog. <https://www.superprof.co.uk/blog/maths-and-the-modern-world/>
- Saputro, T., Herlina, K., & Distrik, I. (2020). Guided Inquiry Based Students' Worksheet to Grow Students' Critical Thinking and Communication Skills. , 3, 18-26. <https://doi.org/10.24042/IJSME.V3I1.5146>.
- Sari, R., Rosjanuardi, R., Herman, T., Isharyadi, R., & Balkist, P. (2024). Development of Mathematics Interactive E-Worksheet. *The Eurasia Proceedings of Science Technology Engineering and Mathematics*. <https://doi.org/10.55549/epstem.1521959>.
- Savas, V. & Beverly, M. (2024). Using the CRA Framework in Elementary Math. <https://www.edutopia.org/article/using-cra-framework-elementary-math/>
- Schoenfeld, A. H. (2016). *How we think: A theory of human decision-making with some educational applications*. Routledge. 10.4324/9780203843000.
- SEA-PLM (Southeast Asia Primary Learning Metrics) Main Regional Report) 2019
- Skemp, R. R. (1976). Relational understanding and instrumental understanding. *Mathematics Teaching*.
- Sukasno, S., Zulkardi, Z., Putri, R., & Somakim, S. (2024). The Design of Student Worksheets on Integer Material Using the Context of Musi Rawas Tourism. *Jurnal Math Educator Nusantara: Wahana Publikasi Karya Tulis Ilmiah di Bidang Pendidikan Matematika*. <https://doi.org/10.29407/jmen.v10i2.21640>.
- Sustainable Development Goals (2023). United Nations Department of Economic and Social Affairs. <https://www.un.org/en/our-work>
- Tabor, P., Dibley, D., Amy J. Hackenberg, A., & Norton, A. (2020) *Numeracy for All Learners: Teaching Mathematics to Learners with Special Needs*. SAGE Publications Ltd (UK).
- Tessa School (2024). *Fostering Conceptual Understanding in Tessa International School's Math Curriculum*. Tessa International School. <https://tessais.org/fostering-conceptual-understanding>
- Tobias, S. (1993). *Overcoming math anxiety*. W.W. Norton & Company.
- Topçiu, Marta & Myftiu, Johana. (2015). Vygotsky Theory on Social Interaction and its Influence on the Development of Pre-School Children. *European Journal of Social Sciences Education and Research*. 4. 172. 10.26417/ejser.v4i1.p172-179.
- Vygotsky, L. S. (1978). *Mind in society: The development of higher psychological processes*. Harvard University Press.
- Warren, C. (2024). *Math Education Insights: Boosting Student Performance with Concrete and Semi-Concrete Representations*. Book Nook.

- <https://blog.booknook.com/math-education-insights-boosting-student-performance-with-concrete-and-semi-concrete-representations>
- White, I. (2024). Unlocking the Power of Numeracy in Math Education.
<https://www.india-white.com/unlocking-the-power-of-numeracy-in-math-education/>
- Widodo, S. A., Wijayanti, A., Irfan, M., Pusporini, W., Mariah, M., & Rochmiyati, S. (2023). Effects of worksheets on problem-solving skills: Meta-analytic studies. *International Journal of Educational Methodology*, 9(1), 151-167.
<https://files.eric.ed.gov/fulltext/EJ1378744.pdf>
- World Economic Forum (2023). OECD PISA results: Maths and reading skills in 'unprecedented drop'. Here's why that matters (2023). World Economic Forum.
<https://www.weforum.org/stories/2023/12/oecd-pisa-results-maths-reading-skills-education/>
- Zarate, E., Fernandez B., & Dorias, L. (2022). Downloaded Worksheets: A Learning Activity to Enhance Mathematical Level. *Universal Journal of Educational Research*.
-